

A bibliography of multimodal research: 1980s — 2015

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The bibliography is not exhaustive:

- The table does not contain edited volumes or conference papers.
- The table does not contain references to work in multimodal interaction analysis (see e.g. references in Scollon & Scollon 2009, Norris 2009).

The table columns are organized according to the area of interest (from left to right):

1. Print media
2. Digital media
3. Photography
4. Film / television
5. Theory

1980s

Eiler (1987)

1990s

Royce (1998)

Kress & van Leeuwen (1998)

Allen et al. (1999)

O'Halloran (1999)

2000s

Bell & Milic (2002)

Delin & Bateman (2002)

Guo (2004)

Cheong (2004)

Holsanova & Holmqvist (2006)

Royce (2007)

Matthiessen (2007)

Maiorani (2008)

Guijarro & Pinar Sanz (2008)

Liu & O'Halloran (2009)

Francesconi (2011)

Feng (2011)

Guijarro (2011)

Kress & van Leeuwen (1990)

O'Toole (1994)

Kress & van Leeuwen (1996)

Forceville (1996)

van Leeuwen (1996)

Thibault (2000)

Kress & van Leeuwen (2002)

Iedema (2003)

Stöckl (2004)

Lim (2004*a, b*)

Bateman et al. (2004)

Baldry & Thibault (2005)

Stöckl (2005)

Martinec & Salway (2005)

Lenke (2005)

Kong (2006)

Bateman (2008)

O'Halloran (2008)

Jewitt (2009)

Thomas (2009)

Zhao (2010)

Elleström (2010)

van Leeuwen (2011)

Bateman (2011)

Bell (2001)

Thibault (2000)

Kok (2004)

Machin (2004)

O'Halloran (2004)

van Leeuwen (2005)

Knox (2007)

Bateman et al. (2007)

Hopearuoho & Ventola (2009)

Knox (2009)

Maiorani (2009)

Stenglin & Djonov (2010)

Caple (2009)

Caple & Bednarek (2010)

Bateman (2009)

Tan (2009)

Tseng & Bateman (2010)

Tan (2010)

Eisenlauer (2011)

Djonov & van Leeuwen (2011*a, b*)

Maier (2011)

Berazhuy (2012)
Hiippala (2012*a*)

Taboada & Habel (2013)
Bowcher & Liang (2013)
Kong (2013)
Martin (2014)
Francesconi (2014)
Acartürk et al. (2014)

Eisenlauer (2013)
Sindoni (2013)

Caple (2013)

Bateman & Schmidt (2012)
Tseng & Bateman (2012)
Wildfeuer (2012)
Bateman & Veloso (2013)
Tseng (2013*a,b*)
Wildfeuer (2014)
Bateman (2013)

Hiippala (2012*b*, 2013)
Boeris & Holsanova (2012)
Waller (2012)
Norris (2013)
Martinez (2013)
Cohn (2013)
Forceville (2014)
Bateman (2014)
Norris & Maier (2014)
Thomas (2014)
Bateman & Wildfeuer (2014)

Hiippala (2015)

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